

INFLUENCE OF AGE AND MARITAL STATUS ON THE SEXUAL BEHAVIOUR OF FEMALE STUDENTS IN UNIVERSITIES IN THE SOUTH WEST NIGERIA

T. O. Owuamanam and E. O. Osakinle

Department of Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Education, University of Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the influence of age and marital status on the sexual behaviour of female students in Universities in the South West Nigeria. A questionnaire designed and validated by the researchers was used to collect data from a sample of 1000 female students. Multi-stage sampling techniques were used to select the subjects.

Two null hypotheses were postulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Scheffé Post-hoc tests. The finding revealed that age of female students and marital status influenced the students' sexual behaviour while on campus. Based on the finding, it is recommended that important information on sexual behaviour and consequences should be provided based on their ages and marital status.

KEYWORDS: Influence, sexual behaviour, marital status, female students, universities, south west,

INTRODUCTION

Sexual behaviour is a concept that involves different types of sexual activities. Owuamanam (1982) listed various types of sexual activities of Nigerian adolescents, which include kissing, breast and genital fondling, embracing, holding hands and sexual intercourse. Sexual intercourse seems to be common among Nigerian youths. Virginity in girls is no longer highly valued and the age at which young ones have their first intercourse is reducing. Today's young people seem to become sexually active at increasing younger age. In addition, some studies have shown that few adolescents use contraceptives and are at risk of pregnancy and HIV/AIDS (McCauley and Salter, 1995 and Orubuloye, 1997).

The attitude of youths to sex can be described as carefree.

The possible consequences of youths' sex life is a major concern to all citizens, particularly, guidance counselors, social workers and health workers.

In the Comet Newspaper of 9th March, 2005, Dr. Kalu Uduka, Coordinator, Abia State Action committee on AIDS reported that 3.7% of the State's population were AIDS/HIV carriers and that over 70% of the number were youths. He maintained that 85% of the infection was through sexual intercourse. The Commissioner for Health in Abia State in Nigeria, Dr. Kalu Udukwe suggested that the war against AIDS could be won if the people could change their sexual behaviour. Comet, 9th March, 2005.

The age of youth could be a major factor in unplanned sexual relationship. It is possible that some young girls with relatively little experience are lured into sex. A possible source of danger in this form of sexual relationship is exposure of the girl to unprotected sex. When youths face adults in sexual relationship, they may lack the courage to ask for protected sex probably because of the age difference or the situation they find themselves. Therefore, sexual behaviour of young people in Nigeria even before marriage is an important research problem.

In Nigerian Universities as in other countries, there are students of different marital status (single, married, widowed and separated). Marriage confers on the married unrestricted and unquestionable right to sexual relationship with the spouse, while such relationship with another partner (adultery) is a taboo. Such extra marital relationship also puts the couple at risk of sexually transmitted diseases and HIV/AIDS infection, particularly when engaged in without protection. A married woman in most African cultures is regarded as a “property” of her husband who has no right to personal decision regarding sex. Equally regarded as a taboo is sexual relationship by widowed and separated woman who have not remarried. Marriage tends to restrict woman regarding how they tend to go out with other men. The singles are not tagged and therefore they have all the time and chance to go out with anybody they like. It is not likely that married, widowed and separated University female students respect cultural sanctions regarding sexuality given the relative freedom in the Universities and after often reported sex boom in these Universities. It is of research interest to examine if the sexual behaviour of single, married, widowed and separated female University students is different.

The purpose of the study therefore was to find out whether such variables as age of University female students and their marital status would influence their sexual behaviour. In particular, attention was focused on sexual relationship with extra marital partners, double or multiple partners as well as unprotected sexual and sex without contraceptive.

It was hypothesized that:

1. Age of the female students will have no significant influence on their sexual behaviour;
2. Marital status of female students will have no significant influence on their sexual behaviour

METHOD

A descriptive design of the survey type was used for this study. The sample consisted of 1000 female students drawn out of five Universities (University of Ado-Ekiti,, Olabisi Onabanjo university,Ago-Iwoye,, University.of Lagos,Lagos, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Federal University of Technology, Akure.) in the South West Nigeria using stratified random sampling technique. Two hundred female students were selected from each of the five Universities.

A questionnaire titled ‘Sexual Behaviour Questionnaire (SBQ)’ designed by the researchers was used to collect data for the study. The questionnaire sought information about the sexual activities the subjects engaged in with their sexual partners and whether or not they used contraceptives or protected themselves from infection when they engaged in sexual intercourse. The questionnaire was found to have a validity coefficient of 0.65 and reliability coefficient of the data collected were analyzed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Scheffe-post-hoc tests and the null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Hypothesis 1: Age of the female students will have no significant influence in their sexual behaviour.

Table 1: Summary of One-Way Analysis of Variance of Age of Students and Sexual Behaviour.

Source Y	D.F	Sum of Squares	Mean of Squares	F.Cal	Table Value
Between groups	5	22711.30	4542.236		
Within groups	983	250210.70	254.54	17085	2.21
Total	985	272922.00			

P > 0.05

Table 1 is a One-Way ANOVA of six age groups namely, age group below 15 years, 16-20, 21-25, 26-30, 31-35 and 36 and above, and their sexual behaviour. The ANOVA on sexual behaviour of age groups below 15 years, 16-20, 21-25, 26-30, 31-35, and 36 and above showed a calculated f-value of 17.85 which is greater than the table value of 2.21. The hypothesis that the age of students will have no significant influence on female students’ sexual behaviour is rejected. There is a

significant difference in the sexual behaviour of female students belonging to different age groups. Further analysis using Scheffe-post-hoc test was carried out on the behaviour of students of different age groups to determine their order of significance as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Scheffe-Post-Hoc test Comparison on Age Groups

S/N	Age Group	Mean X	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	Below 15 years	98.33						
2	16-20 Years	100.76						
3	21-25 Years	102.86						
4	26-30 Years	108.95	*	*				
5	31-35 Years	115.14	*	*	*			
6	36 and above	116.33	*	*	*			

*Denotes pairs of group significantly different at 0.05 level of significance.

The result shows there is significant difference in sexual behaviour between Group 1 (below 15 years) with a mean of 98.33 and Group 4 with a mean of 108.95, Group 5 (31-35 years) with a mean of 115.14 and Group 6 (36 and above) with a mean of 116.33. Also, there is a significant different between Group 2 (16-20 years) with a mean of 100.76 and Group 4 (26-30 years) with a mean of 108.95, Group 5 (31-35 years) with a mean of 102.86 and Group 6 (36 and above) with a mean of 116.33. Finally, there is a significant difference in sexual behaviour between Group 3 (21-25 years) with a mean of 115.14 and Group 5 (31-35 years) with a mean of 115.14 and Group 6 (36 and above) with a mean difference of 116.33. The age group with most significant sexual behaviour is Group 6 (36 and above) with a mean value of 116.33. Age appears to play a very important role in sexual behaviour of female students. It appears that the older the students are, the more they tend to engage in sexual activities.

Hypothesis 2: Marital status of female students will have no significant influence on their sexual behaviour.

Table 3: One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) On Marital Status and Female Students Sexual Behaviour

Source Y	D.F	Sum of Squares	Mean of Squares	F.Cal	Table Value
Between groups	4	11469.67	2867.42		
Within groups	957	258430.48	270.04	10.62	2.37
Total	961	269900.15			

P < 0.05

Table 3 shows that the value of F calculated (10.62) is greater than the table value. The hypothesis is therefore rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in the sexual behaviour of female students of different marital status. Although all the marital status groups are significantly different in their sexual behaviour, further analysis using Scheffe post-hoc test was carried out as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Scheffe Post-Hoc-Test on Marital Status

S/N	Age Group	Mean X	1	2	3	4	5
1	Single	101.51					
2	Married	106.33					
3	Divorced	108.35					
4	Widow	109.38					
5	Separated	110.3	*				

* Denotes pairs of groups significantly different.

One can easily concluded that from Table 4 group 5 (separated) with the highest mean of 110.3 is the most significantly different in sexual behaviour with group 1 (singles).

DISCUSSION

The result showed that there is a significant different in sexual behaviour of female students of different age groups and that the most significant difference was observed between age group above 36 years and the other age groups. Age is therefore an important factor in sexual behaviour. It is expected that as people grow older, they should be more involved in sexual activities in terms of frequency and variety of the act. This is because older people are expected to be more mature sexually and more experienced in sexual act. The individual is expected to be more exposed and more knowledgeable about protection from infection and unwanted pregnancy and can therefore engage in sexual activities with relatively less anxiety.

The result further showed that marital status influenced female students' sexual behaviour and that the single female students were more involved in sexual activities than the married ones. Culturally, married women whether in intact homes, separated or widowed are to be cautious about their sexual behaviour. They are expected to remain faithful to their husband whether living with them, separated or dead. They have limited freedom to take decisions about their sexuality. Sexual relationship with their husbands could have been reduced by their living on campus away from the husbands. This explanation supports William, et. al (1998) that the sexual behaviour of married women may be controlled because they may want to be faithful to their partners. Islam (1996) reasoned that this could be to keep themselves free from sexually transmitted infections.
et. al should be typed in italics

REFERENCES

- Islam, O. M. (1996): STDs: The Burden and the Challenge. AIDs Captions Family Health International. 3(1) 4-7.
- McCauley, A. P. and Salter, C. (1995): Meeting the Needs of Young Adults. Population Reports Series J No. xxxiii pg. 1-2.
- Orubuloye, I. O. (1997): Adolescent Sexual and Reproductive Health. An Unpublished Paper Delivered at Mac Arthur Foundation Ibadan, Oyo State.
- Owuamanam, D. O. (1982): Sexual Activities of School-Going Adolescents in Nigeria. *Adolescence* 17(65) 81-87.
- William, G. Milligan, A. and Odemuwingle, T. (1998): A Common Cause: Young People Sexuality and HIV/AIDs in Three African Countries. Published by Actionaid Hamlyn House: Macdonald Road Arch Way, London, UK. With UNAADS, 20 Avenue Appia CH-1211, Geneva, Switzerland.

Received for Publication: 16/05/2008

Accepted for Publication: 01/06/2008

Corresponding Author

E. O. Osakinle

Department of Guidance and Counseling, Faculty of Education, University of Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria